

AN EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS FOR THE CHARGING CYCLE OF A HYDRO-PNEUMATIC ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEM

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Keywords: OFFSHORE ENERGY STORAGE, HYDRO-PNEUMATIC ENERGY STORAGE, PROTOTYPE SCALED-MODEL EXPERIMENTS, HYDRAULIC PUMP EFFICIENCY, HYDRAULIC SECONDARY PRESSURE LOSSES

Abstract

A novel new Hydro-Pneumatic Energy Storage (HPES) system is currently being developed primarily for use in offshore environments. Recent studies have focussed on the thermodynamic characteristics of the storage system; particularly on the energy stored within the pressure vessels. Thus, an Energy Conversion Unit was tested to better understand the hydraulic performance of the HPES system ancillaries. The aim of this study focussed on the charging cycle of the system. Results have shown that the main losses within the system pertain to losses within the hydraulic pump assembly and to hydraulic frictional losses within the flow circuit. With regards to the hydraulic pump, efficiencies ranging from 40% to 80% were obtained, with the pump operating at higher efficiencies when the overall system pressure was higher. As for the hydraulic losses, it was observed that these are solely dependent on the system operational water flow rate and were not affected by the system operational pressure. Hydraulic losses resulted in a system hydraulic efficiency ranging between 65% to just under 100%. Overall system efficiency thus fell within the range of 27% to 80%, with the system operating in more favourable conditions as the pressure increased.

1. Introduction

With the current push to reduce overall greenhouse gas emissions, multiple projects and solutions are being studied to help achieve this goal through the use of renewable energy sources. Energy storage solutions are consequently being investigated since these can help integrate larger amounts of renewable energy generation in electrical power grids.

Currently, a team at the University of Malta (UM) is working on the development of a prototype Energy Storage System (ESS) particularly for use in offshore environments. The concept, called the Floating Liquid-piston Accumulator using Seawater under Compression (FLASC) system, is a mechanical concept of energy storage which falls under the category of Hydro-Pneumatic Energy Storage (HPES) devices. In FLASC, electrical energy that is to be stored is first converted into hydraulic energy through the use of a hydraulic pump and the pressurised hydraulic supply is then injected into a pressure vessel which is also pre-charged with compressed air. During this process, the water being injected into the pressure vessel acts as a liquid piston. This reduces the volume of the air trapped inside the pressure vessel, thus also increasing its pressure with the resulting energy being stored in the form of potential pneumatic energy. When electrical energy is required from the storage system, the process is reversed. In this case, the trapped air inside the pressure vessel is allowed to expand and expel the water inside the pressure vessel, thus providing a source of hydraulic power. This is then used to power a hydraulic turbine coupled to a generator, which generates the required electrical energy. Examples of such systems were evaluated by Wang et al. [1], Odukomaiya

et al. [2] and Camargos et al. [3]. Of particular relevance is the study by the team at UM on FLASC, [4]. A basic schematic of a HPES system is provided in Fig. 1.

Recently, the UM team had the possibility to evaluate the performance of a small-scale FLASC prototype installed in Dock 1, Birgu, in Malta's Grand Harbour. The results from this experiment had shown that the system was very promising, with the scale-model achieving a round trip thermal efficiency of around 93 % [5]. It should be noted however, that such experiments were focussed primarily on the storage aspect of the HPES system and specifically on the thermodynamic aspects of the air undergoing compression and expansion inside the pressure vessels. In this case, the round-trip efficiency was calculated as the ratio of the energy supplied to, and then recovered from the pressure vessels, with the system energy and power being calculated at the inlet of the main pressure vessel. The performance of the rest of the system, such as the pump and hydraulic system, was not examined in detail. This was also the case in the GLIDES project [2]. With reference to Fig. 1, the attention of such studies was primarily focussed on the pressure vessel on the left-hand side of the schematic.

The present study focuses on the hydraulic losses incurred in the charging system of a topside Energy Conversion Unit (ECU), the latter comprising a hydraulic pump, hydraulic turbine for energy recovery and the associated hydraulic components. The ECU is indicated in Fig. 1. The tests were conducted on a prototype kilowatt-scale ECU being built in the Fluids Laboratory of the Faculty of Engineering at the University of Malta. This is enabling a better understanding of

the different losses present in the ECU components used for charging the HPES system. Such losses were primarily related to the operational losses at the pump, and to secondary losses due to flow inside the system's hydraulic circuit (i.e. components such as hoses, manifolds, fittings and valves). The energy storage performance of the pressure vessel, or Pressure Containment System (PCS) itself, was not within the scope of this current study. It should also be noted that desalinated water was used in these experiments.

Fig. 1 – Schematic of a HPES system

2. Experimental Setup

A schematic of the setup used in the experiments carried out on the ECU in the UM Fluids Laboratory is presented in Fig. 2. Note that the sensors used and their locations within the system are marked with their respective schematic symbols.

Fig. 2 – Schematic of the ECU setup for pressure vessel charging used during the laboratory experiments

The hydraulic circuit between the pump and the pressure vessel was split up into three hydraulic sections, with the details of the different components used in each section listed in Table 1.

In this setup, electrical power was first supplied from the grid to the hydraulic pump assembly. In the pump assembly, electrical power was first converted into rotational kinetic

energy at the pump's electrical motor, which in turn powers the hydraulic pump. The hydraulic supply then flows through the three different sections before then being injected into the pressure vessel at the end of the hydraulic circuit used during the charging cycle.

Table 1 – Hydraulic circuit sections

Section	Component	Internal diameter
A	- Pump outlet	1¼" – 31.75mm
	- Hose, 40 cm length	1¼" – 31.75mm
	- Flow meter	1" – 25.4mm
	- Check valve	1¼" – 31.75mm
B	- 1 st half of main manifold	2" – 50.8mm
	- 2 nd half of main manifold	2" – 50.8mm
	- Elbow fitting	1¼" – 31.75mm
	- Electrically controlled ball valve	1¼" – 31.75mm
	- Secondary flow meter (not in use)	1" – 25.4mm
	- Hose, 2 m length	1¼" – 31.75mm
C	- 1 st half of secondary manifold	1¼" – 31.75mm
	- 2 nd half of secondary manifold	1¼" – 31.75mm
	- Elbow fitting	1" – 25.4mm
	- Ball valve	1" – 25.4mm
	- Hose, 1.5 m length	1" – 25.4mm
	- Elbow fitting	1" – 25.4mm
	- Pressure vessel inlet	2" – 50.8mm

It should be noted that the main manifold is used to split the flow of the system to other components during other operational modes of the ECU, whilst the secondary flow is to act as the main connection point to the different pressure vessels. In this case, only one pressure vessel was used, with this being connected to one of the four connection ports of the secondary manifold.

The pressure vessel used was sized at 1,000 L, with the vessel being placed in a vertical orientation and with the hydraulic supply inlet placed at the bottom of the vessel. Since no volume measurement sensors were used, it was imperative to ensure that the different charging cycle runs were carried out with the same initial level of water inside the pressure vessel.

2.1 Sensor Setup

Four pressure sensors were used to monitor the pressure across the ECU hydraulic circuit, whilst a flow meter placed at the pump outlet was used to record the system operational flow rate. Table 2 lists the different sensors used, their location inside the hydraulic circuit, and the variable terminology used. The sensor locations are noted in the schematic shown as Fig. 2.

Table 2 – Sensor list

Sensor	Location	Variable
Pressure sensor 1	Pump Outlet	p_1 (bar)
Pressure sensor 2	Main Manifold	p_2 (bar)
Pressure sensor 3	Secondary Manifold	p_3 (bar)
Pressure sensor 4	Pressure Vessel	p_4 (bar)
Flow Meter	Pump Outlet	Q (l/min)

It should be noted that the data generated by the sensors were stored in a Campbell Scientific CR1000 data logger with a sampling rate of 1 Hz. Pressure sensors 1, 2 and 3 have an accuracy of ± 0.12 bar, pressure sensor 4 has an accuracy of ± 0.3 bar, whilst the flow meter has an accuracy of ± 1.35 l/min.

The pump had an internal controller and sensors, with these being set up such that the variable speed drive also recorded the main data at a rate of 1 Hz. Table 3 lists the different pump data outputs and their variables.

Table 3 – Pump data output

Pump variable	Variable
Pump motor power input	P_{pump} (W)
Pump motor speed	N (rpm)

2.2 Pump Selection, Ancillary Components and Water Supply

The pump selected was a diaphragm positive displacement pump since this is capable of delivering high operating pressures at low flow rates, thus increasing the storage density of the HPES system. It should be noted that the pump motor was fitted with a variable frequency drive (VFD) which allows for the control of the pump's operational speed. The pump's electrical motor was rated to 22 kW. It should be noted that the pump motor was fitted with a reduction gearbox set to a ratio of 1:1.24.

The ECU was designed to have a set of pump ancillary components to ensure that the hydraulic pump was operating within the required inlet parameter conditions. In this case, desalinated water was first collected by means of a submersible pump from an underground water cistern located beneath the Fluids Lab. The water collected was then passed through a fine mesh filter to ensure that any particulate matter, which might damage the hydraulic pump's diaphragms, was removed. The water was then stored inside the 1,000 L water storage tank (described also as a buffer tank). This tank ensured a constant and plentiful supply of water to prevent the pump from running dry. The pump inlet was connected to the buffer tank via a 2 ½" suction hose.

It should be noted that losses pertaining to the pump supply section (including power consumed by the supply pump and losses due to the filter and other fittings), were not included in this current study.

3. Methodology

The experimental process consisted of a number of charging cycles of the HPES system for different pump operational speeds and at different pressure ratios.

Table 4 lists the different pump speeds used, with these being set by means of the pump's VFD. Table 5 lists the different pressure ratios used, with these being set via the pre-charge pressure of the pressure vessel. In total, 20 different charging conditions were tested, with all experiments reaching a peak pressure of 32 bar.

Table 4 – Pump operational speeds

Pump Speed Setting	Speed (N , rpm)	Flow Rate (Q , l/min)
20% (SP20)	285	30
40% (SP40)	570	60
60% (SP60)	855	90
80% (SP80)	1140	120
100% (SP100)	1425	150

Table 5 – Pressure ratios and pressure ranges

Pressure Ratio (R_p)	Pre-Charge Pressure (bar)
1.5	21.3
2.0	16.0
2.5	12.8
3.0	10.7
Peak Pressure	32.0

3.1 Preparation

Before commencing with a charging cycle, the system required pre-charging to the air's initial (pre-charge) pressure, as listed in Table 5. This was carried out using an air compressor connected directly to the pressure vessel. It should be noted that in order to ensure a constant water level inside the pressure vessel during all the runs, the pressure vessel was emptied completely before each pre-charging procedure.

Since the air inside the pressure vessel heats up during the pre-charging procedure (i.e. when using the air compressor), the pressure vessel was allowed to cool down sufficiently after pre-charging before commencing a hydraulic charging cycle run. In certain cases, a top-up of compressed air was required to ensure that the pre-charge pressure was at the required level.

3.2 Charging Cycle Procedure

Once it was ensured that all the sensors were operating correctly and that the buffer tank was primed with enough water, it was then possible to start the pump at the required operational speed via the pump's VFD. The system was then monitored as the pressure vessel was injected with water supplied by the pump, increasing the pressure of the trapped air by means of the liquid-piston. The charging process was considered as complete once the internal pressure in the pressure vessel reached 32 bar. At this point, the pump was switched off.

3.3 Turn-over Procedure

Once a charging cycle was completed and the data stored, the system was discharged via an outlet valve located on the main manifold, with the water in the pressure vessel being returned to the underground water cistern. It should be noted that the outlet valve was closed as soon as the pressure vessel was emptied completely. Since the trapped air cools during discharge, the system pressure was allowed to settle before commencing another charging cycle. It should be noted that in certain cases, air might have escaped during the discharging process, calling for a top up with the air compressor to ensure

that the initial pre-charge pressure inside the pressure vessel was always the same.

4. Results

4.1 Pump Operation

The first results to be discussed are those pertaining to the performance of the hydraulic pump. Fig. 3 shows the electrical power absorbed by the pump for the five speed settings for a pressure ratio of 1.5, whilst Fig. 4 shows the corresponding readings for a pressure ratio of 3.0. The curves show the gradual increase in the power absorbed by the pump during the increase of pressure as water is injected into the pressure vessel, compressing the air via the formed liquid piston.

Fig. 3 – Pump electrical power input for the different pump speed settings for a pressure ratio of 1.5

Fig. 4 – Pump electrical power input for the different pump speed settings for a pressure ratio of 3.0

The results obtained show that the pump power requirement was primarily related to the speed at which it was operated and on the system pressure. The initial system pressure (pre-charge pressure) had no effect on pump performance, except for the fact that the charging cycle was longer for higher pressure ratios. The resultant final, peak pump power input, at which

the pressure vessel pressure reached 32 bar, was equal for all the experiments carried out at the same pump speeds, irrespective of the experiment's pressure ratio. Similar trends were obtained for the experiments carried out using pressure ratios of 2.0 and 2.5.

Pump efficiency was calculated using the following equation:

$$\eta_{pump} = \frac{p_1 \times Q}{P_{pump}} \quad Eq. 1$$

It should be noted that the pump efficiency calculated using Eq. 1 is an efficiency that covers losses present in the whole pump assembly, with this including losses in the variable speed drive, the electrical motor, the speed reduction gearbox and the hydraulic positive displacement pump.

Fig. 5 – Pump efficiency against pressure vessel pressure for experiments using a pressure ratio of 1.5

Fig. 6 – Pump efficiency against pressure vessel pressure for experiments using a pressure ratio of 3.0

The results provided in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show the pump efficiency for the experiments carried out using pressure ratios of 1.5 and 3.0 respectively. Both graphs show that the resultant pump efficiency was not dependent on the operational experiment pressure ratio but was primarily dependent on the

operational speed of the pump and on the system pressure. The graphs for pressure ratios of 2.0 and 2.5 exhibited similar characteristics.

Of note (see Fig. 5 and Fig. 6) are the ripples present in the data output from the pressure sensors, with these also being present throughout the rest of the results presented. This is due to the pump's diaphragms, which produce a pulsating supply of pressurised water.

As also shown in both Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, the pump starts off with a low operational efficiency, which then increased as the system pressure increased. Of note is the difference in efficiency at the same pressure point for the different pump speeds, where a higher efficiency was obtained for lower pump speeds. This indicates that as the pump speed increased, so did the frictional losses inside the pump assembly, leading to increased losses.

The increase in efficiency as the pressure increased may be attributed to low loading on the pump assembly as compared to its design specification. It should be noted that the pump and its electrical motor were sized for operation up to a pressure of 83 bar, with the nominal rating of the pump's electrical motor being 22 kW.

Fig. 7 – Pump efficiency against pressure vessel pressure for experiments using a pump speed setting of 60%

Fig. 7 shows how the efficiency of the pump, in this case operating at a 60% pump speed setting, changes only with system pressure and is nearly unaffected by the pressure ratio. The difference in results between the different experiments may be attributed to other external factors (such as the pump operational temperature) which were not being monitored.

Fig. 8 presents a plot of the relationship between the pump operational efficiency and the pump's electrical motor load ratio; this being a ratio of the pump power input to the motor rating (22 kW). From this result it is apparent that although the load ratio is noticeably lower for the slower pump speed settings throughout the experiment duration, the efficiency achieved as the pressure increased was still higher than that achieved during the experiments conducted at higher load ratios at the higher pump speed. This contrasts with a regular motor efficiency curve (as provided in Fig. 9) where the efficiency is expected to increase as the load increases. Thus, the increase in efficiency as noted from the experiments

carried out on the ECU was not primarily related to the increase of the load on the electrical motor since the highest pump efficiency was actually achieved at an electrical motor load of less than 10%.

Fig. 8 – Pump operational efficiency against pump electrical motor load ratio

Fig. 9 – Typical electrical induction motor efficiency curve as a function of load [6]

The source of the increase in efficiency as the system pressure increased may be attributed to the hydraulic pump and its mode of operation. This occurs possibly due to the operation of the diaphragms inside the pump head, which could be working more efficiently as the system pressure increases. It should be noted that when considering an operational pressure ratio of 3.0 (with a pressure range of 10.7 to 32 bar), the pump would be operating within an operational pressure range of 12.9% to 38.6% when compared to the pump's rated operational pressure of 83 bar. Unfortunately, since the pressure vessel used was rated for up to 32 bar, it was not possible to carry out experiments at higher pressures to study the effect of the system pressure on the performance of the hydraulic pump. Extrapolating the trends shown in Fig. 7 suggests that higher efficiencies would be achievable when operating at higher pressures.

Another possible source of increase in efficiency as the system pressure increases is the efficiency of the gearbox. As noted by Clavac et al. [7], a gearbox's efficiency increases as torque increases, whilst keeping a constant speed.

4.2 Pressure Drops across Hydraulic Circuit

The pressure drops across each section (as listed in Table 1 and in Fig. 2) were calculated by applying Bernoulli's principle in the following equations:

$$\Delta p_A = p_1 + \frac{\rho Q^2}{2A_{pump}^2} + \rho g H_{pump} - p_2 - \frac{\rho Q^2}{2A_{main}^2} - \rho g H_{main} \quad Eq. 2$$

$$\Delta p_B = p_2 + \frac{\rho Q^2}{2A_{main}^2} + \rho g H_{main} - p_3 - \frac{\rho Q^2}{2A_{second}^2} - \rho g H_{second} \quad Eq. 3$$

$$\Delta p_C = p_3 + \frac{\rho Q^2}{2A_{pump}^2} + \rho g H_{second} - p_4 - \frac{\rho Q^2}{2A_{main}^2} - \rho g H_{PV} \quad Eq. 4$$

$$\Delta p_{ECU-Charging} = \Delta p_A + \Delta p_B + \Delta p_C \quad Eq. 5$$

where:

- A_{pump} and H_{pump} refer to the hydraulic area and vertical height of the pump outlet;
- A_{main} and H_{main} refer to the hydraulic area and vertical height of the main manifold;
- A_{second} and H_{second} refer to the hydraulic area and vertical height of the secondary manifold; and
- A_{PV} and H_{PV} refer to the hydraulic area and vertical height of the pressure vessel inlet.

It should be noted that since the pressure vessel's pressure sensor was located at the top of the vessel, it did not take into account the increase in pressure at the pressure vessel's inlet (located at the bottom of the vessel) due to the weight of the vertical column of water. Unfortunately, no volume or level sensors were available and thus there was no reliable method to accurately measure the increase in pressure due to the water present in the pressure vessel. However, it should be noted that a thermal imaging camera was used to observe the water level and it was noted that the water did not reach a level higher than around 1.2 to 1.5 m above the pressure vessel inlet. These water heights were obtained at the end of a charging cycle when there was the largest volume of water inside the pressure vessel. This means that the largest pressure increase due to the water inside the pressure vessel was of less than 0.15 bar. Thus, when compared to the operational pressure of 32 bar obtained at the end of said cycles, the increase in pressure due to the height of the water column may be considered to be negligible.

A sample result showing the pressure drop for section A using a pressure ratio of 3.0 is provided in Fig. 10. As noted in the graph, although the pressure drop fluctuates due to pump operation, the overall time-averaged pressure drop remains constant throughout the cycle, irrespective of the system

pressure. Thus, an average pressure drop may be calculated for the different pressure drops in each section using the different operational pressure ratios and pump speed settings.

Fig. 10 – Sample result for pressure drop across section A for the experiments using a pressure ratio of 3.0

Table 6 – Table listing pressure drops across section A

Rp	Δp_A				
	SP20	SP40	SP60	SP80	SP100
1.5	0.074	0.512	1.207	2.007	2.898
2.0	0.074	0.506	1.191	2.037	3.010
2.5	0.074	0.493	1.265	1.920	2.983
3.0	0.100	0.610	1.133	1.982	2.983

Table 7 – Table listing pressure drops across section B

Rp	Δp_B				
	SP20	SP40	SP60	SP80	SP100
1.5	0.032	0.118	0.261	0.365	0.688
2.0	0.033	0.130	0.261	0.407	0.684
2.5	0.032	0.116	0.254	0.358	0.662
3.0	0.032	0.115	0.261	0.406	0.662

Table 8 – Table listing pressure drops across section C

Rp	Δp_C				
	SP20	SP40	SP60	SP80	SP100
1.5	0.278	0.416	0.638	0.953	1.287
2.0	0.290	0.424	0.644	0.953	1.307
2.5	0.292	0.434	0.647	0.977	1.321
3.0	0.307	0.431	0.653	0.963	1.301

Table 9 – Table listing pressure drops across ECU hydraulic circuit during charging cycle

Rp	$\Delta p_{ECU-Charging}$				
	SP20	SP40	SP60	SP80	SP100
1.5	0.384	1.047	2.107	3.325	4.872
2.0	0.397	1.061	2.095	3.397	5.001
2.5	0.398	1.043	2.166	3.254	4.966
3.0	0.438	1.155	2.047	3.351	4.946

Table 6 to Table 8 show the average pressure drops across the different sections, whilst Table 9 shows the sum of the pressure drops across the three sections, thus resulting in the overall pressure drop across the full hydraulic circuit inside the ECU during the charging cycle.

From the results obtained it is apparent that the largest pressure drop occurred within section A, with this most probably being due to the check valve which presents a noticeable constriction within its assembly. It should be noted that as expected, the pressure drops increased as the flow rate increased for higher pump speed settings.

Using these results, it was then possible to calculate the power losses in each section, and hence the overall efficiency of the section when compared to the power input into that section. The hydraulic efficiencies of each section, along with the overall ECU hydraulic efficiency for the charging circuit, were calculated using the following equations:

$$\eta_A = \frac{Q(p_1 - \Delta p_A)}{Qp_1} \quad Eq. 6$$

$$\eta_B = \frac{Q(p_1 - \Delta p_A - \Delta p_B)}{Q(p_1 - \Delta p_A)} \quad Eq. 7$$

$$\eta_C = \frac{Q(p_1 - \Delta p_A - \Delta p_B - \Delta p_C)}{Q(p_1 - \Delta p_A - \Delta p_B)} \quad Eq. 8$$

$$\eta_{hydro} = \eta_A \times \eta_B \times \eta_C \quad Eq. 9$$

Fig. 11 to Fig. 13 show the hydraulic efficiency for sections A, B and C respectively, whilst Fig. 14 shows the ECU's overall hydraulic efficiency during the charging cycle. It should be noted that the results for the experiments conducted using pressure ratios of 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 achieved the same results, albeit for a cropped time frame.

Since section A experienced the highest pressure drops, this yielded the lowest hydraulic efficiency when compared to losses across the other two sections. It should be noted that as the pressure increased, so too did the hydraulic efficiency of each section. This is due to the fact that whilst the system pressure increased, the pressure drops and flow rates (and hence, power losses) across the hydraulic circuit remained constant, thus reducing the effect of the pressure and power

losses due to secondary hydraulic losses on the efficiency of the hydraulic circuit.

Fig. 11 – Graph showing section A's hydraulic efficiency

Fig. 12 – Graph showing section B's hydraulic efficiency

Fig. 13 – Graph showing section C's hydraulic efficiency

Fig. 14 – Graph showing the ECU's overall hydraulic efficiency during the charging cycle

4.3 Section K-values

Since the pressure drops and flow rates are known for each section, it was thus possible to evaluate a frictional losses K-value within each section and for the overall system. This was carried out by using the follow equation:

$$\Delta p = K \frac{(\rho v^2)}{2} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

where:

- v^2 is the flow velocity within the section.

Graphs were then plotted for the three different sections and for the ECU's overall pressure drops, with the pressure drops plotted against $\frac{\rho v^2}{2}$. Linear trendlines were then plotted to obtain the required K-values for each section. The results and their fit are tabulated in Table 10. The linear regression plot for the K-value for section A is shown in Fig. 15 as an example.

Table 10 – Results obtained for the different sections' K values

Section	K-Value	Trendline fit (R^2)
A	60.732	0.9986
B	13.187	0.9959
C	28.497	0.9628
Overall ECU	102.42	0.9957

These results provide a value which may be used to estimate the pressure losses within each section for different pump operational speed settings, irrespective of the operational pressure ranges and ratios.

Fig. 15 – Graph showing pressure drops in section A against the calculation of $\frac{\rho v^2}{2}$ for the different charging cycles

4.4 Overall ECU Efficiency during charging cycle

By combining the results obtained from the pump and hydraulic circuit efficiency, it was possible to derive a value for the ECU's overall charging cycle efficiency. This covers all system losses, from the losses in the pump assembly, to the losses within the hydraulic circuit up to the inlet of the pressure vessel. The ECU's overall charging cycle efficiency was thus calculated using the following equation:

$$\eta_{\text{overall-charging}} = \eta_{\text{pump}} \times \eta_{\text{hydraulic}} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 show the overall ECU charging cycle efficiency against time and system pressure respectively for the experiments carried out at a pressure ratio of 3.0. The experiments using pressure ratios of 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 yielded the same results, albeit with shorter timeframes and reduced pressure ranges.

Fig. 16 – Graph of the ECU's overall charging cycle efficiency against time

Fig. 17 – Graph of the ECU’s overall charging cycle efficiency against system pressure

As noted from the previous sections, the overall system efficiency increased with time, particularly as the overall system pressure increased. The highest pump speed setting at 1,425 rpm had the lowest efficiency of all the runs since this yielded the highest pressure drop due to hydraulic secondary losses, along with the lowest pump operational efficiency due to friction. As the system pressure increased, the overall system efficiency increased as well since the hydraulic pump becomes more efficient as the system pressure increases, whilst the overall effect of the pressure drops becomes less noticeable when compared to the overall system pressure.

5. Conclusions

The experiments conducted on the ECU undergoing charging cycles yielded positive results. The system’s overall charging cycle efficiency fell within the range of 60 to 80% at the peak system pressure of 32 bar for different pump operational speeds. The overall charging cycle efficiency includes losses present in the system between the electrical power input to the hydraulic pump to the delivery of hydraulic power stage at the pressure vessel inlet.

The losses in the system may be primarily attributed to the pump operational efficiency and to hydraulic pressure losses due to the flow inside the system’s components. The losses vary depending on the situation. The pump operated at higher efficiencies as the system pressure increased, whereas the hydraulic losses due to hydraulic flow remained constant throughout the experiment, with these being dependent solely on the pump’s operational speed setting.

During testing, it was noted that the system was not operated at its intended operational pressure particularly with regards to the hydraulic pump assembly. This was due to the fact that the pressure vessel used was only rated to a maximum operational pressure of 32 bar. Thus, further studies are required when this system is operated at its intended maximum operational pressure of 64 bar in order to further evaluate the performance of the hydraulic pump assembly. Furthermore, additional

studies need to be conducted on this ECU and other similar setups to cover the design optimisation of the system, particularly with regards to the pump selection (which is dependent on the particular setup used).

It should be noted that the experiments focussed only on the charging cycle phase of the ECU. Further studies are now required on the discharge aspect of the system and in particular, on the performance of the hydraulic turbine to regenerate electricity from the pressurised hydraulic supply exiting the pressure vessel. Once this is completed, it would be possible to have a better understanding of the performance and efficiency of the system for a complete operational cycle: i.e. from initial charging to storage and finally to discharge at the water turbine.

6. Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 862252 (Project MUSICA - Multiple Use of Space for Island Clean Autonomy).

This project is also supported through the Maritime Seed Award 2021 (Project SimHyDFlow).

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